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ABSTRACTS

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Green Gold Rush: Elevating Biobutanol Brilliance through Smart Pretreatment

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Abstract: Biofuels are a category of renewable energy sources derived from organic materials, such as plants, algae, or waste residues. They represent a crucial aspect of sustainable energy solutions, offering a viable alternative to traditional fossil fuels. The production and use of biofuels contribute to mitigating climate change, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and enhancing energy security.

This study explores the pretreatment of pineapple peel waste, a cost-effective feedstock, using a high-pressure reactor and various enhancers. Optimal conditions with a binary acid at 130 °C yielded a remarkable 80.17% hemicellulose solubilization. Fermentation of pooled fractions with *Clostridium acetobutylicum* NRRL B 527 resulted in 6.5 g/L butanol production with a yield of 0.14 g butanol/g sugar. This signifies a milestone in utilizing pineapple peel waste for bioenergy, showcasing its potential as an eco-friendly and economically viable resource. The study contributes to sustainable energy solutions by efficiently converting low-cost feedstock into biofuels, addressing both environmental and economic considerations.

Keywords: Biobutanol, Chemical pretreatment, Fermentation, Pineapple peel, Renewable energy

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